

Highlights

Comparison of Various Temporal Air Traffic Flow Management Models in Critical Scenarios

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- When compared to a model based on greedy regulations, cherry-picking measures could dramatically reduce the total delay
 - Hybrid models combining regulations for major overloads with cherry-picking measures for residuals would likewise reduce the total delay, while having less impact on the maximum delay per airspace user item
- The air traffic flow management models presented herein provide a road map for the gradual implementation of a futuristic optimal framework to support human decision-making in critical scenarios

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Abstract

Overloads (i.e., critical imbalances between traffic demand and capacity) are currently resolved in the European air transportation network by activating air traffic flow management regulations. Flights subject to regulations are delayed on the ground by the computer assisted slot allocation system, which uses a first-planned, first-served principle to allocate the delays. In the last decades, many researchers have proposed alternative models based on more or less complex optimisation techniques, which could effectively resolve overloads with less delay. Despite the fact that these models were very promising, changing the current operational system and procedures - which trust is supported by a successful working history dating back to 1995 - may not be realistic in the short term. This paper examines the gradual transition from current air traffic flow management to a futuristic model in which flights are assigned delays with massive cherry-picking measures that minimise the total delay in the network, without necessarily adhering to the first-planned, first-served rule. A reference model with greedy regulations representative of current operations is compared to a model where the Network Manager optimises regulations using hyper-heuristics, a model based on massive cherry-picking measures, and hybrid models that consider regulations to resolve major overloads and cherry-picking measures only for residual overloads. These models are compared in critical scenarios with major capacity issues caused by adverse weather conditions. Results suggest that hybrid models could be a viable option for reducing delays with minor changes in the current air traffic flow management paradigm.

Keywords: Air traffic flow management, demand-capacity balance, adaptive large neighbourhood search

1. Introduction

Adapting capacity to demand is the first step in aligning demand and capacity. This can be accomplished by modifying the airspace configuration, for example. If demand still cannot be met, air traffic flow management (ATFM) measures are implemented to match demand with available capacity. At present, the most common measure in Europe consists of limiting the rate at which aircraft enter congested traffic volumes¹ during a given period of time, i.e., to activate regulations. The flights subject to one or several regulations are issued with a ground delay on a first-planned, first-served basis by the Computer Assisted Slot Allocation (CASA) system (Network Manager, 2018) so that the maximum entry rates in the corresponding traffic volumes are not exceeded during the regulated periods. It is worth noting that CASA is a heuristic algorithm, not an optimisation procedure, that airspace users recognise as equitable because it applies the same rules to all flights. The reader is referred to Vranas (1996) and the references therein for further details about the rules used by CASA to assign and manage delays.

The different flow managers across Europe, in collaboration with the Network Manager, are those who decide when and where to apply regulations to resolve overloads in their area of responsibility. Because of the complex interactions between the active regulations in the network, this implies that the global (i.e., network-wide) delay is primarily governed by the judgements of different humans to resolve their own, local, problems. Even though humans can handle simple scenarios with moderate overloads efficiently, their performance is expected to deteriorate in critical scenarios (e.g., when severe convective weather causes a substantial drop of capacity over a vast region). In this context, countless scientists have been interested for many decades in designing models for optimising ATFM measures at the network level.

In parallel to the deployment of CASA, Vranas (1996) and Bertsimas and Patterson (1998) proposed the presumably first models of the so-called slot allocation problem, which could be solved by using standard mixed-integer programming (MIP) optimisation solvers. Results revealed that the solution

¹A traffic volume is related to a single geographical *entity* (either an aerodrome, a set of aerodromes, an airspace sector or a point), and may consider all traffic passing through that entity or only specific flows.

32 of these models could significantly reduce the total delay, when compared to
33 the use of regulations and CASA in the same conditions. The main challenge
34 at that time was the execution time of the optimisation solvers.

35 Remarkable advances in optimisation solvers have enabled real-time com-
36 putation of network-wide optimal slot allocations, and a new wave of models
37 has emerged in the recent years. For instance, Ivanov et al. (2017) proposed a
38 model that minimises delay propagation to subsequent flights, simultaneously
39 increasing flight adherence to departure slots at coordinated airports. Bolić
40 et al. (2017) also proposed a model that can be solved in short computation
41 times for large-scale instances. A variant that also considers aircraft rota-
42 tions through the turn-around time constraints was proposed by Pellegrini
43 et al. (2017). Recently, Bolić et al. (2021a) introduced a model that also
44 quantifies the flexibility (by means of time windows) of each flight, and a
45 convenient way of presenting the solutions of this model to the flow man-
46 agers was proposed in a complementary publication (Bolić et al., 2021b).
47 Finally, Xu et al. (2020) proposed a collaborative ATFM framework aiming
48 to improve the cost-efficiency for airspace users, which also considers alter-
49 native trajectories with re-routing and/or level capping in addition to delay.

50 The current ATFM paradigm, however, is far from a model that as-
51 signs specific delays to individual flights with a logic rather opaque to the
52 airspace user. Even though the aforementioned research studies demon-
53 strated through realistic use cases that the total delay could be reduced
54 by adopting optimisation models, the current slot allocation by the CASA
55 algorithm is regarded as equitable by airspace users, and is a legacy and
56 trusted method that has proven to ensure safe flight operations since 1995.

57 The main contribution of this paper is to examine the transition from the
58 current ATFM paradigm based on regulations (not necessarily optimal) and
59 CASA, to a futuristic model in which flights are assigned individual delays
60 by solving a global slot allocation problem. In particular, a baseline model
61 representative of current operations in which regulations are put in place
62 greedily to resolve local overloads is compared with (1) a model in which
63 regulations are optimised by using the adaptive large neighbourhood search
64 (ALNS) algorithm (2) a model in which massive cherry-picking measures are
65 issued as a result of solving the slot allocation problem and (3) two hybrid
66 variants that resolve major overloads with optimal regulations and only use
67 cherry-picking measures to deal with the residual overloads. The comparison
68 is carried out for several critical scenarios during the summer of 2019 with
69 major capacity issues due to convective weather over France and Spain.

70 The various ATFM models examined in this paper were designed in the
71 scope of the ISOBAR project (Artificial Intelligence Solutions to Meteo-
72 Based DCB Imbalances for Network Operations Planning), and the critical
73 scenarios are those selected for the human-in-the-loop validation exercises
74 with the French and Spanish flow managers of the area control centres in-
75 volved in the project. ISOBAR is an exploratory research project funded by
76 the Single European Sky ATM Research (SESAR) Joint Undertaking that
77 aims at integrating enhanced convective weather forecasts for predicting ca-
78 pacity reductions (Jardines et al., 2021), and ATFM models build on artificial
79 intelligence to select mitigation measures at local and network level in a col-
80 laborative way. The paper will briefly mention the machine learning models
81 that improve convective weather forecasts and predict capacity reductions,
82 but they are beyond the scope of this paper. This paper only covers the
83 ATFM models of the ISOBAR’s network operations planning service.

84 The document is organised as follows. Section 2 presents the basic model
85 of the slot allocation problem, as well as the working principles of the ALNS
86 algorithm. Then, Section 3 describes the various ATFM models compared in
87 the experiment. The setup of the experiment and the results of the compari-
88 son are covered in Sections 4 and 5, respectively. Finally, Section 6 concludes
89 the paper with a discussion and recommendations for future work.

90 2. Mathematical background

91 The purpose of this section is to provide the background required to follow
92 the definition of the various ATFM models described in Section 3.

93 2.1. Slot allocation problem

94 The objective of the slot allocation problem is to minimise the total de-
95 lay, subject to the fact that each flight must be assigned one and only one
96 delay and that the traffic demand cannot exceed the capacity in any time
97 window monitored for any traffic volume (keep in mind that a traffic volume
98 relates to a single geographic entity, such as an airport or an airspace sector).
99 Equation (2) formalises the basic model of the slot allocation problem. The
100 indicator function that appears in Eq. (2) is:

$$1_{\tau}(w) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if the time } \tau \text{ falls within the time window } w \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Nomenclature

Scalars

- Λ Duration of the time windows (min)
 λ Slice of the time windows (min)
 D Maximum delay per flight (min)

Sets

- $\mathcal{E} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ Flights that are exempted from ATFM measures (e.g., airborne)
 \mathcal{F} All flights
 $\mathcal{F}_v \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ Flights crossing the traffic volume v
 \mathcal{V} Traffic volumes
 \mathcal{W} Time windows
 $\mathcal{W}_v \subseteq \mathcal{W}$ Time windows monitored for the traffic volume v (see Fig. 1)

Variables

- x_{fd} Flight f is assigned delay d

Parameters

- $\gamma_{vw} := \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_v \cap \mathcal{E}} \mathbb{1}_{\tau_{vf}}(w)$ Exempted demand in the traffic volume v during the time window w (i.e., demand that cannot be adjusted)
 κ_{vw} Capacity of the traffic volume v during the time window w
 τ_{vf} Estimated time over (ETO) the traffic volume v for flight f
 $\tilde{\kappa}_{vw} := \kappa_{vw} - \gamma_{vw}$ Spare capacity of the traffic volume v during the time window w , after subtracting the exempted demand

Figure 1: Time windows monitored for an hypothetical traffic volume v , considering different combinations of duration and slice. Each magenta bar represents a time window $w \in \mathcal{W}_v$. The width denotes the duration (min), while the height represents the number of flights which ETO falls within the time window. The capacity is indicated by the horizontal orange line. Each time window is associated a capacity value κ_{vw} .

$$\min_{x_{fd}} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F} \setminus \mathcal{E}} \sum_{d=0}^D x_{fd} d \quad (2a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{d=0}^D x_{fd} = 1 \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F} \setminus \mathcal{E}, \quad (2b)$$

$$\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}_v \setminus \mathcal{E}_v} \sum_{d=0}^D x_{fd} \mathbb{1}_{\tau_{fv}+d}(w) \leq \tilde{\kappa}_{vw} \quad \forall w \in \mathcal{W}_v, v \in \mathcal{V}, \quad (2c)$$

$$x_{fd} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F} \setminus \mathcal{E}, d = 0, \dots, D. \quad (2d)$$

101 For a complete list of variants, the reader is encouraged to look into the
 102 works cited in Section 1, Vossen and Ball (2006) and Castelli et al. (2011).

103 2.2. Adaptive large neighbourhood search

104 In this paper, a hyper-heuristic algorithm (i.e., heuristic to automatically
 105 select simpler heuristics) has been used to optimise regulations network-wide.
 106 Recently, heuristics based on large neighbourhood search (LNS) (Shaw, 1998)
 107 have shown outstanding performance in solving a wide variety of transporta-
 108 tion problems (see for instance the work by Wolfinger (2021) and the refer-
 109 ences therein). LNS gradually improves the initial solution \mathbf{x}_0 by alternately
 110 *destroying* and *repairing* it. The steps of LNS are listed in Algorithm 1.

111 The basic idea behind LNS is to alternate between feasible and infeasible
 112 regions. At each iteration, the destroy heuristic creates an infeasible solution,
 113 which is brought back into the feasible region by the repair heuristic. It is
 114 worth noting that the destroy and repair heuristics can be thought of as
 115 fix-and-optimise operations, respectively. In particular, the fix operation
 116 (equivalent to the destroy heuristic) freezes some variables of the solution to
 117 their current values, whereas the optimise operation (equivalent to the repair
 118 heuristic) improves the solution by modifying the variables that are free.

119 According to Algorithm 1, at each iteration of the LNS algorithm a new
 120 candidate solution \mathbf{x}' is generated as a result of applying the destroy and re-
 121 pair heuristics to the current solution \mathbf{x} . The candidate solution replaces the
 122 current solution if it satisfies the acceptance criteria, otherwise is discarded.

123 The acceptance criteria can be implemented in different ways. Despite
 124 the simplest choice is to only accept better solutions, other methods such as

Algorithm 1 Large neighbourhood search (LNS)

Require: \mathbf{x}_0
1: $\mathbf{x} \leftarrow \mathbf{x}^* \leftarrow \mathbf{x}_0$
2: **repeat**
3: $\mathbf{x}' \leftarrow \text{REPAIR}(\text{DESTROY}(\mathbf{x}))$
4: **if** $\text{ACCEPT}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ **then**
5: $\mathbf{x} \leftarrow \mathbf{x}'$
6: **if** $c(\mathbf{x}) < c(\mathbf{x}^*)$ **then**
7: $\mathbf{x}^* \leftarrow \mathbf{x}$
8: **end if**
9: **end if**
10: **until** TERMINATION
11: **return** \mathbf{x}^*

125 simulated annealing are often implemented in order to reduce the chances of
126 getting stuck in local minima (Santini et al., 2018).

127 If the objective function of the candidate solution $c(\mathbf{x})$ is better than
128 the best found so far, it becomes the new optimal solution \mathbf{x}^* . Finally,
129 the algorithm terminates when a certain condition is triggered, e.g., after a
130 number of iterations, when the maximum execution time is exceeded, when
131 the best objective has not improved during a given number of iterations, etc.

132 Note that the destroy heuristic must be designed in such a way that
133 the entire search space can be reached, i.e., it cannot constantly focus on
134 destroying the same part of the solution. For this reason, some degree of
135 randomness is commonly introduced in the destroy heuristic. Conversely, in
136 most implementations the repair heuristic makes use of variants of the greedy
137 paradigm, e.g. performing the locally best (or least bad) action from the
138 currently infeasible solution. Using this kind of design, the destroy heuristic
139 guarantees diversification, while the repair heuristic fosters intensification.

140 LNS uses one destroy and one repair heuristic. Adaptive large neighbour-
141 hood search (ALNS) is an extension of LNS originally introduced by Ropke
142 and Pisinger (2006), which allows multiple destroy and repair heuristics to be
143 used during the optimisation process. ALNS (Algorithm 2) was designed on
144 the premise that different problem instances, and even different solutions to
145 the same problem, are managed with varying success by distinct heuristics.
146 ALNS uses a simple yet effective mechanism to learn the likelihood that an
147 heuristic will generate a good candidate (Pisinger and Ropke, 2010).

148 Let Ω^- and Ω^+ be the catalogue of possible destroy and repair heuristics,
 149 respectively. Both Ω^- and Ω^+ must be defined by the user. Each heuristic
 150 has an associated weight, which determines the likelihood of selecting the
 151 heuristic at each iteration. The vector of weights of the destroy and repair
 152 heuristics are denoted by \mathbf{w}^- and \mathbf{w}^+ , respectively. The probability to select
 153 the i^{th} destroy and the j^{th} repair heuristics is given, respectively, by:

$$p_i^- = \frac{w_i^-}{\sum_{k=1}^{|\Omega^-|} w_k^-}; \quad p_j^+ = \frac{w_j^+}{\sum_{k=1}^{|\Omega^+|} w_k^+}. \quad (3)$$

154 That is, the higher the weight of an heuristic, the more likely it will be
 155 selected to destroy/repair the current solution during the optimisation.

156 The weight of the different heuristics must be updated in order to increase
 157 the probability of selecting successful heuristics, and to decrease that of less
 158 effective ones. In order to accomplish this goal, the quality $\delta \in \mathfrak{R}$ of the
 159 candidate solution generated by the current destroy and repair heuristics is
 160 determined at each iteration of the algorithm. The quality of the heuristics
 161 depends on its success. In particular:

$$\delta = \begin{cases} \delta_* & \text{if } \mathbf{x}' \text{ is the better than } \mathbf{x}^* \\ \delta_b & \text{else if } \mathbf{x}' \text{ is better than } \mathbf{x} \\ \delta_a & \text{else if } \mathbf{x}' \text{ is not better than } \mathbf{x} \text{ but is accepted} \\ \delta_r & \text{Otherwise } (\mathbf{x}' \text{ is rejected}), \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

162 where $\delta_{(\cdot)}$ are fixed parameters of the algorithm, determined by the user.

163 After determining the quality of the candidate solution with Eq. (4), the
 164 weights of the destroy and repair heuristics that generated the candidate
 165 solution are updated according to:

$$w_i^- = \rho\delta + (1 - \rho)w_i^-; \quad w_j^+ = \rho\delta + (1 - \rho)w_j^+, \quad (5)$$

166 where the decay factor $\rho \in (0, 1) \subset \mathfrak{R}$ controls the influence of the recent
 167 success of the applied heuristic on its weight.

Algorithm 2 Adaptive large neighbourhood search (ALNS)

Require: $\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{w}_0^-, \mathbf{w}_0^+$

- 1: $\mathbf{w}^- \leftarrow \mathbf{w}_0^-$
 - 2: $\mathbf{w}^+ \leftarrow \mathbf{w}_0^+$
 - 3: Initialise \mathbf{p}^- and \mathbf{p}^+ according to Eq. (3)
 - 4: $\mathbf{x} \leftarrow \mathbf{x}^* \leftarrow \mathbf{x}_0$
 - 5: **repeat**
 - 6: DESTROY \leftarrow Sample from Ω^- according to \mathbf{p}^-
 - 7: REPAIR \leftarrow Sample from Ω^+ according to \mathbf{p}^+
 - 8: $\mathbf{x}' \leftarrow$ REPAIR (DESTROY (\mathbf{x}))
 - 9: **if** ACCEPT (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') **then**
 - 10: **if** $c(\mathbf{x}') < c(\mathbf{x}^*)$ **then**
 - 11: $\delta \leftarrow \delta_*$
 - 12: $\mathbf{x}^* \leftarrow \mathbf{x}'$
 - 13: **else if** $c(\mathbf{x}') < c(\mathbf{x})$ **then**
 - 14: $\delta \leftarrow \delta_b$
 - 15: **else**
 - 16: $\delta \leftarrow \delta_a$
 - 17: **end if**
 - 18: $\mathbf{x} \leftarrow \mathbf{x}'$
 - 19: **else**
 - 20: $\delta \leftarrow \delta_r$
 - 21: **end if**
 - 22: Update \mathbf{w}^- and \mathbf{w}^+ according to Eq. (5)
 - 23: Update \mathbf{p}^- and \mathbf{p}^+ according to Eq. (3)
 - 24: **until** TERMINATION
 - 25: **return** \mathbf{x}^*
-

168 3. Temporal air traffic flow management models

169 In this paper, an ATFM solution of a model is composed of a set of
170 regulations \mathcal{R} and/or a set of cherry-picking measures \mathcal{P} . Each regulation is
171 characterised by the traffic volume identifier, the start time, the end time,
172 and the regulation rate (in entries per hour). As is done in current operations,
173 the CASA algorithm determines the delay allocated to each regulated flight,
174 given the set of regulations. Each cherry-picking measure consists of the delay
175 assigned to a specific flight. The cost of a solution is the total delay generated
176 by the corresponding ATFM measures (regulations and cherry-picking).

177 This section presents the ATFM models compared in the experiment.

178 3.1. Temporal cherry-picking

179 The temporal cherry-picking model (CP) consists of assigning optimal
180 delays to individual flights by solving the slot allocation problem described
181 by Eq. (2). That is, the CP attempts to find the best solution that could
182 be achieved in the absence of constraints other than capacity. The optimal
183 solution only includes a set of cherry-picking measures, without regulations.

184 It should be noted that the CP takes the capacity constraints as hard
185 constraints. That is, all of them must be satisfied, otherwise the optimisation
186 problem is considered infeasible and no solution is returned. While this
187 feature may appear to be advantageous (since it assures that overload-free
188 solutions are produced), it may actually cause problems if the input data are
189 not accurate. Furthermore, the CP is the only model considered in this study
190 capable of proving the solution’s local optimality in a rigorous mathematical
191 sense. Finally, since the CP is less constrained than the others because flights
192 do not have to adhere to the first-planned, first-served rule of CASA, the
193 hypothesis is that the global delay will be lower than for the other models.

194 3.2. Greedy regulations

195 The greedy regulations model (GR) consists of creating regulations in an
196 iterative way until all time windows are free of overloads. Algorithm 3 lists
197 the steps of the algorithm used to generate a solution with the GR.

198 Algorithm 3 starts by identifying the set of time windows that are over-
199 loaded given the traffic demand and the declared capacity. In this process,
200 both windows of 20 min duration slicing every 20 min as well as windows
201 of 60 min duration slicing every 20 min are monitored (see Fig. 1). It is

Algorithm 3 Greedy regulations

Require: Traffic demand & capacity

- 1: Identify overloaded time windows taking into account `overload_20` and `overload_60` tolerances
 - 2: **repeat**
 - 3: Activate a new regulation on every overloaded time window, using the corresponding capacity as regulation rate
 - 4: Group consecutive regulations with same rate within the same traffic volume (or which gap is lower than a `max_gap` tolerance)
 - 5: Remove regulations which duration is less than `min_duration`
 - 6: Run the CASA algorithm
 - 7: Shift the traffic demand according to the delays assigned by CASA
 - 8: Identify overloaded time windows taking into account `overload_20` and `overload_60` tolerances
 - 9: **until** All overloads are resolved
 - 10: **return** Set of regulations that resolve overloads in a greedy way
-

202 worth noting that certain tolerances may be taken into account when de-
203 ciding whether or not an entry counts value that exceeds a time window's
204 capacity is considered to be an overload. For instance, an overload could
205 exist if and only if the entry counts value on a 20 min (resp. 60 min) window
206 is 15% (resp. 5%) higher than the capacity. These tolerances are denoted as
207 `overload_20` and `overload_60`, respectively, and the default value is 0%.

208 At each iteration, regulations are activated on the overloaded time win-
209 dows, using the corresponding capacity as regulation rate. Then, consecutive
210 regulations with same rate within the same traffic volume (or which gap is
211 lower than a `max_gap` tolerance) are grouped. Following this step, regula-
212 tions which duration is less than another parameter, called `min_duration`,
213 are removed. Finally, the CASA algorithm is executed with the current set of
214 regulations, the traffic demand is shifted according to the delays assigned by
215 CASA, and overloads are identified again in the new situation. Algorithm 3
216 stops when all overloads are resolved by the current set of regulations. The
217 solution of the GR aims at roughly representing current ATFM practises.

218 3.3. *Optimal regulations*

219 As the name implies, the greedy regulations model presented above cre-
220 ates regulations to resolve overloads in a greedy, albeit blind, manner. Ac-

221 cordingly, the solution that results from the optimisation process may be
222 far from optimal. The optimal ATFM regulations model (OR) consists of
223 improving the solution proposed by the GR using the ALNS algorithm de-
224 scribed in Section 2.2. The motivation for using ALNS is that (1) the cost
225 function and constraints are very non-linear due to the complexity of CASA
226 and so classical optimisation algorithms like MIP are not appropriate, (2) the
227 combinatorial is extremely large due to the many possibilities of regulating
228 a big set of traffic volumes over a long period of time but (3) the algorithm
229 should produce a high quality solution in an acceptable amount of time.

230 Section 2.2 described the working principle of the general-purpose ALNS
231 algorithm. The designer must specify the following functions in order to tailor
232 the ALNS algorithm to a specific problem: the initial solution generator, the
233 catalogue of DESTROY and REPAIR heuristics (Ω^- and Ω^+ , respectively),
234 the ACCEPT criteria, and the TERMINATION criteria.

235 3.3.1. Initial solution

236 The initial solution is a key component of presumably any optimisation
237 algorithm, because the closer the initial solution to the (unknown) optimal
238 solution, the less time it will take to converge. Generating high-quality initial
239 solutions, however, may be difficult and/or time consuming. In most of the
240 cases, there exists a trade-off between the quality of the initial solution and
241 the time it takes to generate it. In this paper, Algorithm 3 has been adopted
242 to generate good initial solutions in a short amount of time.

243 3.3.2. DESTROY heuristics

244 In this paper, three different DESTROY heuristics have been defined,
245 which select a subset of regulations to be removed from the current feasi-
246 ble solution. As discussed in Section 2.2, any destroy heuristic should in-
247 clude some randomness in order to foster exploration. For this reason, a
248 $\beta \in (0, 1) \subset \mathfrak{R}$ percentage of the regulations are randomly removed from the
249 current solution as a result of the destroy phase. The probability of each
250 regulation being removed is determined by the specific destroy heuristic:

251 *High delay.* The objective of this heuristic is to explore solutions with a high
252 potential of decreasing the objective function. Accordingly, the likelihood of
253 each regulation being removed from the solution is proportional to the ATFM
254 delay that it generates: the higher the delay, the greater the probability.

255 *Low efficiency.* The efficiency of a regulation is defined as the ratio between
 256 the number of flights that have the regulation as most penalising (MPR)², and
 257 the total number of flights affected by the regulation. A regulation concerning
 258 a lot of flights which delay is forced by other regulations is considered as
 259 inefficient. When using this heuristic, the likelihood of each regulation being
 260 removed from the solution is inversely proportional to its efficiency.

261 *Random.* It assigns the same probability to all regulations.

262 3.3.3. REPAIR heuristic

263 As discussed in Section 2.2, any REPAIR heuristic should optimise the
 264 variables that are free after the destroy phase, while keeping those fixed un-
 265 touched. After the destroy phase, some overloads will most likely be formed
 266 as a result of cancelling a percentage of the regulations; alternatively, the
 267 repair phase could be effectively skipped and more regulations destroyed.

268 In this paper, a single repair operator has been defined, which acts greedily
 269 by regulating overloaded time windows with Algorithm 3. Note that, in
 270 contrast to the generation of the initial solution, where Algorithm 3 starts
 271 from scratch (i.e., from a clean solution without regulations), the repair
 272 heuristic starts with the destroyed solution, which (likely) has some regu-
 273 lations in place. This implies that the traffic demand has the effect of these
 274 regulations. Algorithm 3 can only add more regulations, but cannot remove
 275 existing ones (which comprise the fixed variables in the destroy-repair argon).

276 3.3.4. ACCEPT criteria

277 In this paper, simulated annealing has been adopted for the ACCEPT
 278 criteria. Using this method, each candidate solution \mathbf{x}' is accepted with
 279 probability $\exp \frac{c(\mathbf{x}) - c(\mathbf{x}')}{T}$, where T is the so-called temperature. The initial
 280 temperature T_0 is chosen so that an hypothetical candidate solution that is ϵ
 281 percent worse than the initial solution \mathbf{x}_0 has a 50% percent chance of being
 282 accepted. Accordingly:

$$T_0 = \epsilon \frac{c(\mathbf{x}_0)}{\log 2}. \quad (6)$$

²Note that a flight may be subject to more than one regulation simultaneously. In this case, the delay of the regulation that allocates the greatest delay (the most penalising) takes precedence. That is, the slot in each one of the other regulations will be forced according to the delay assigned by the most penalising regulation.

283 The temperature is decreased by a factor ϕ in each iteration. That is, as
284 the search progresses the algorithm tolerates fewer and fewer deteriorating
285 solutions. Both ϵ and ϕ are fixed parameters to be defined by the user.

286 3.3.5. TERMINATION criteria

287 In the current implementation, the ALNS algorithm stops after a given
288 number of destroy-repair iterations, also determined by the user.

289 3.4. Hybrid

290 In between the CP and the OR, one could envisage a hybrid model that
291 addresses major overloads by using regulations, and cherry-picking measures
292 only to solve the residual overloads. The balance between cherry-picking
293 and regulation measures is adjusted by the definition of the major overloads
294 concept, which could be based on simple metrics like entry and/or occupancy
295 counts above capacity, or more sophisticated metrics like complexity. In
296 this paper, the distinction between minor and major overload is based on a
297 deterministic threshold applied to entry counts above the capacity.

298 The hybrid model consists of executing the OR and the CP in cascade:
299 first, the OR optimises the set of regulations such that entry counts above
300 the capacity in 20 and 60 min windows do not exceed `overload_20` and
301 `overload_60`, respectively. Then, the CP solves the residual overloads by as-
302 signing delays to specific flights not subject to regulations, i.e., flights subject
303 to regulations after the OR are exempted from cherry-picking measures.

304 4. Description of the experiment

305 The goal of the experiment was to compare various temporal ATFM mod-
306 els in critical scenarios, where humans would struggle to deal with them ef-
307 fectively at regional level. The parameters of the ATFM models compared
308 in this experiment are listed in Section 4.1. Then, Section 4.2 describes the
309 critical scenarios that were selected for the comparison.

310 4.1. ATFM models

311 In this experiment, the performance of the CP, GR, OR and hybrid mod-
312 els described in Section 3 were compared. For the hybrid model, two variants
313 were considered: the standard hybrid (H), which is closer to the OR than to
314 the CP, and the hybrid *plus* (H+), which is closer to the CP than to the OR.
315 Table 1 particularises the parameters of the various ATFM models.

Table 1: Parameters of the various ATFM models

Algorithm	Parameter	ATFM model			
		CP	H+	H	OR GR
Greedy regulations (Algorithm 3)	<code>overload_20</code>	-	0.30	0.15	0.
	<code>overload_60</code>	-	0.10	0.05	0.
	<code>max_gap</code> (min)	-		60	
	<code>min_duration</code> (min)	-		0	
ALNS (Algorithm 2)	<code>iterations</code>	-		200	-
	$(\delta_*, \delta_b, \delta_a, \delta_r)$	-	(3, 2, 1, 0.5)		-
	β	-		0.2	-
	ρ	-		0.8	-
	ϵ	-		0.05	-
Slot allocation problem (Eq. (2))	D (min)		90		-
	λ (min)		20		-
	Λ (min)		20		-

316 According to Table 1, the GR and OR must find overload-free solutions
317 only with regulations. The hybrid variants, on the other hand, allow some
318 residual overloads to be subsequently solved with cherry-picking measures:
319 the H allows entry counts exceeding up to 5% and 15% the declared capacity
320 in windows of 60 and 20 min, respectively. The H+ is more permissive,
321 doubling these tolerances to 10% and 30%, respectively. These values were
322 recommended by operational experts from the Network Manager.

323 For GR, OR, H and H+, regulations separated by less than 60 min within
324 the same traffic volume are grouped together under the same regulation, in
325 order to avoid too short and unrealistic gaps between consecutive regulations.

326 The OR, H and H+ perform 200 destroy-repair iterations to find out the
327 best set of regulations in the solution³. At every iteration, 20% of the active
328 regulations are removed as a result of the destroy phase, and the decay factor
329 for the weights in Eq. (5) is 0.8. In the first iteration, any candidate solution
330 5% worse than \mathbf{x}_0 is accepted with 50% probability, and the temperature of
331 the simulated annealing at each iteration is 99.5% the previous iteration's
332 value. Similar values are typically adopted in the literature (Lutz, 2014).

³In this paper it was observed that the ALNS algorithm converges after approximately 150 destroy-repair iterations. Furthermore, the convergence of the algorithm is exponential: high-quality solutions are found during the first iterations, and the improvement after more than 100 iterations is, in most of the cases, marginal. It is also important to remember that, as with any heuristic, the solution's optimality cannot be proven.

333 For the CP, the maximum delay per flight is 90 min. A lower value would
334 result in more evenly distributed delays among flights, but it would also
335 increase the risk of failing to identify a feasible solution.

336 Finally, in order to mimic as accurate as possible the current operational
337 system, the replica of the real CASA algorithm included in the EUROCON-
338 TROL’s R-NEST (research network strategic monitoring tool) was used.

339 *4.2. Critical scenarios*

340 In this experiment, the performance of the various ATFM models were
341 compared for several traffic situations, corresponding to the morning (AM)
342 and afternoon (PM) periods of four very busy days during summer 2019:
343 26th and 27th of July, and 9th and 27th of August. For the AM period, we
344 considered all flights crossing (i.e., entering) the ACCs subject of study from
345 midnight to noon. For the PM period we considered all flights entering the
346 ACCs from noon to midnight. It is important to note that, in practise,
347 the AM and PM periods cannot be solved separately because some flights
348 entering ACCs during the AM period may be delayed and pushed into the
349 PM period. Keep in mind, however, that this paper presents the results of a
350 human-in-the-loop exercise, where execution time was paramount. Because
351 of this, the AM and PM periods were solved separately in order to achieve
352 reasonable execution times for an interactive simulation. Appendix A shows
353 the typical execution time of the algorithms used by the ATFM models.

354 Furthermore, only flights overflying the ACCs (Area Control Centres)
355 involved in the exercise were considered: Marseille, Reims, Madrid, Barcelona
356 and Palma. The traffic demand for each day and period was obtained from
357 the EUROCONTROL’s Demand Data Repository (DDR). Three different
358 *pictures* of the traffic demand could be obtained from DDR: the initial (last-
359 filled flight plan⁴), the regulated (initial plus delays), and the actual (what
360 was actually flown). Because the regulated demand already has the effect of
361 the regulations that were applied, and the actual demand has further tactical
362 modifications like ATC shortcuts, the initial traffic demand was used.

363 Regarding the declared capacities, one could use the actual opening scheme
364 of each ACC (i.e., which sector configurations were used along the day) as

⁴Strictly speaking, the last-filled flight plan may be also influenced by the actual regula-
tions. Airspace users may re-route to circumvent regulated airspace and thereby mitigate
ATFM delay, for instance. These human actions are captured in the last filled-flight plans.

365 reported in the DDR. Comparing the initial traffic demand with the capaci-
366 ties from the actual opening schemes, however, may result in a large number
367 of exaggerated overloads that are difficult to resolve. In this experiment, the
368 capacities corresponding to two opening schemes were investigated: actual
369 opening schemes from DDR, and opening schemes optimised to minimise
370 overloads subject to manpower constraints. In particular, the EUROCON-
371 TROL’s ICO (improved configuration optimiser) tool (Verlhac et al., 2005)
372 was executed to obtain, for each ACC and traffic situation, the opening
373 scheme from which to extract capacities more in line with demand.

374 The capacities corresponding to the opening schemes of either DDR or
375 ICO were decreased in order to recreate critical scenarios due to convec-
376 tive weather. The capacity reduction figures were derived from a machine
377 learning (ML) model, which was trained on historical regulations and the
378 risk of convective weather provided by the neural network of Jardines et al.
379 (2021). Specifically, the neural network of Jardines et al. (2021) predicts
380 the severity and likelihood (i.e., the risk) of convective weather given a Nu-
381 merical Weather Prediction (NWP) forecast. Then, the ML model uses this
382 risk as input to predict the rate (or capacity) of hypothetical regulations
383 due to weather. Results indicated that the performance of the ML model is
384 satisfactory ($R^2 = 0.82$ and mean absolute error = 2.7 aircraft/hour). Addi-
385 tionally, flow managers involved in the exercise confirmed the quality of the
386 predictions. Accordingly, using the predictions of the ML model or the ac-
387 tual capacity reductions is almost equivalent, and would provide very similar
388 delay figures. It should be noted that the goal of this work is not to present
389 the ML model that predicts capacity reduction, but rather to compare the
390 performance of various temporal ATFM models in critical scenarios.

391 For each traffic situation and opening scheme, two different NWP fore-
392 casts from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF)
393 were used to query the neural network of Jardines et al. (2021) and subse-
394 quently predict the capacity reduction values per traffic volume and hour of
395 the day with the ML model: the forecast made at midnight of the previ-
396 ous day (D-1), and that released at midnight of the same day (D0). The
397 difference between the solutions proposed by a model for the same traffic sit-
398 uation when updating the NWP forecast (and by consequence the capacity
399 reduction figures) aims at capturing its stability. The case without capacity
400 reduction (NA) was also considered for the sake of completeness.

401 Summing up, the total number of traffic situations considered was 4 dates
402 \times 2 periods = 8. For each traffic situation, 2 opening schemes \times (2 capacity

403 reductions due to weather + the case without reduction) = 6 possible capacity
404 situations were evaluated. Accordingly, 8 traffic situations \times 6 capacity
405 situations = 48 scenarios were assessed per ATFM model.

406 5. Results

407 This section presents the main results of the experiment. Section 5.1 thor-
408 oughly describes, for illustrative purposes, the results for one traffic situation.
409 The aggregated performance metrics are presented in Section 5.2.

410 5.1. Illustrative example

411 The traffic situation corresponding to the 27th of July 2019 during the
412 AM period has been selected as illustrative example.

413 5.1.1. Risk of convective weather and capacity reduction prediction

414 Figure 2 shows the risk of convective weather as predicted by the neural
415 network of Jardines et al. (2021) for the 27th of July 2019 at 8AM over the
416 region of interest (at FL320 and FL410), using ECMWF’s NWP forecasts.
417 The risk of convective weather shown in Fig. 2 was used to predict
418 the capacity reduction values at 8AM with the ML model (see Fig. 3).

419 According to Fig. 2, the prediction from Jardines et al. (2021)’s neural
420 network using the NWP forecast made at D-1 suggested many severe con-
421 vective cells over Marseille and Reims ACCs, and few others over Barcelona
422 and Palma ACCs. This figure also shows that the predictions for the NWP
423 forecast generated at D0 were more optimistic, particularly in the vicinity of
424 Marseille and Reims ACCs. Over Barcelona and Palma ACCs, on the other
425 hand, the neural network predicted severe and probable convective cells.

426 The predicted capacity reductions shown in Fig. 3 are in line with the risk
427 presented in Fig. 2. Given the weather forecast created at D-1, the ML model
428 predicted significant capacity reductions in Marseille and Reims ACCs, with
429 values as high as 8 aircraft/hour. The capacity of the other ACCs was also
430 influenced by convective cells, albeit in a more moderate manner. Because
431 of a more optimistic weather forecast, the predicted capacity reductions in
432 Marseille and Reims ACCs were lower at D0. On the other hand, due to the
433 appearance of severe and probable convective cells, the predicted capacity
434 reduction in Barcelona and Palma ACCs increased.

Figure 2: Predicted risk of convective weather for the 27th of July 2019 at 8AM

Figure 3: Predicted capacity reduction for the 27th of July 2019 at 8AM (aircraft/hour)

435 *5.1.2. Overloads*

436 Figure 4 shows the total overload map (i.e., the sum during the AM period
 437 of the 27th of July 2019) in the ACCs of interest, considering time windows
 438 of 20 min slicing every 20 min. Overloads show in Fig. 4 were computed by
 439 comparing the initial traffic demand with the capacities corresponding to the
 440 ICO-optimised opening schemes, lowered in accordance with the predicted
 441 capacity reduction values depicted in Fig. 3.

Figure 4: Total overload for the 27th of July 2019 AM with ICO opening scheme (aircraft)

442 Figure 4 agrees with Fig. 3. The lowest overloads are observed in the first
 443 column, where no capacity reduction due to weather was considered. In the
 444 second column, where the capacities were reduced in accordance with the
 445 capacity reductions predicted at D-1, overloads are much severe, particularly
 446 in the Reims and Marseille ACCs. Due to a more optimistic weather forecast
 447 and consequently smaller capacity reduction, these overloads appear to be
 448 slightly lower in the third column, which corresponds to the D0 forecast.

449 5.1.3. Delay

450 Figure 5 shows the delay map in the region of interest, for the different
 451 models and capacity situations. In particular, Fig. 5 illustrates the total delay
 452 per airspace sector, taking into account all ATFM measures (regulations
 453 and/or cherry-picking) associated with the corresponding traffic volumes that
 454 were applied during the AM period of the 27th of July 2019. Specific per-
 455 formance metrics to support the following discussion, such as the maximum,
 456 average and total ATFM delay, or the number of regulated flights, are re-
 457 ported in the Tables B.2 to B.4 of Appendix B.

458 The total delay of the GR in the case without capacity reduction due to
 459 weather (NA) was 41K minutes, with significant proportion of it attributed
 460 to Marseille ACC. Simply optimising the regulations with the OR resulted
 461 in a 4% delay reduction and a more uniform geographical distribution. With
 462 the H and H+, adding some cherry-picking measures while still using regu-
 463 lations to solve major overloads resulted in a 24 and 36% delay reduction,
 464 respectively. Finally, the CP exhibits a massive total delay reduction (77%).

465 Taking into account the capacity reductions due to convective weather
 466 as predicted by the ML model from the forecast made at D-1, the overloads

Figure 5: Delay for the 27th of July 2019 AM with ICO opening scheme (min)

467 and consequently the delays required to solve them drastically increased.
468 Specifically, the total delay of the GR was 65K min (+37% when compared
469 to the corresponding NA scenario), being Reims ACC the generator of a large
470 percentage of that delay. The OR discovered a combination of regulations
471 reducing the total delay by 13% for this weather forecast, apparently by
472 transferring some of the delay to Marseille ACC.

473 As in the NA scenarios, the delay lowered dramatically as the role of
474 cherry-picking measures became more relevant. In particular, the H and H+
475 found a way to combine regulations and cherry-picking measures decreasing
476 the delay of the GR by 46 and 40%, respectively. Being consistent with the
477 NA situation, the CP proposed a set of cherry-picking measures decreasing
478 the total delay of the equivalent GR solution by 74%.

479 As discussed in previous sections, the weather forecast made at D0 for
480 the traffic situation of this illustrative example was more optimistic than
481 that made at D-1. Accordingly, there should be less delays. For the OR, this
482 proposition is glaringly apparent (see fourth row of Fig. 5).

483 The absolute difference between the delay assigned to a flight when using
484 the forecast made at D-1 and that made at D0 can be also computed for each
485 flight that was delayed in at least one of these two scenarios. Let us call this
486 metric the absolute delay change (ADC). Analysing the ADC distribution can
487 reveal information about the stability of a models across weather forecasts.
488 Stability of the solution is, of course, a desirable property of any model. For
489 the specific scenario examined in this example, the GR and H+ appear to
490 be the most stable in terms of mean ADC, and the hybrid variants show a
491 good trade-off between efficiency and stability of the solution.

492 5.2. Aggregated performance metrics

493 This section presents the aggregated performance metrics, taking into
494 account all the models and scenarios described in Sections 4.1 and 4.2, re-
495 spectively. Specifically, Sections 5.2.1-5.2.3 analyse the delay distribution
496 per flight, airspace user and air navigation service provider, respectively. As
497 in the illustrative example, the graphical results presented in the following
498 sections must be supported by the detailed tables included in Appendix B.

499 5.2.1. Delay distribution per flight

500 Figure 6 shows the delay distribution per flight using *letter-value* box
501 plots, which provide a natural extension of standard box plot for large amounts
502 of data (Hofmann et al., 2011). The median of the distribution is shown as

503 a horizontal line, similar to standard box plot, but letter-value box plot con-
504 veys more information about tail behaviour beyond the whiskers. Figure 6a
505 shows the delay distributions for the scenarios without capacity reduction,
506 as a function of the opening schemes used to derive capacities; while Fig-
507 ure 6b shows the delay distributions for the scenarios with ICO-optimised
508 opening schemes, as a function of the weather forecast used to derive capac-
509 ity reductions. Within each sub-figure of Fig. 6, rows and columns corre-
510 spond to periods and dates, respectively. Furthermore, within each cell of a
511 sub-figure (i.e., a traffic situation), the horizontal axis identifies the various
512 models, ordered from less to more constrained. It is worth mentioning that
513 the overloads for some specific scenarios using the capacities derived from
514 the post-ops opening schemes were so unrealistic that the CP was unable to
515 identify a feasible solution. To ensure a fair comparison, the corresponding
516 runs for the remaining models were removed. That is, Fig. 6 only illustrates
517 the results of a scenario if and only if all ATFM models were successful.

518 Figure 6 shows that, independently of the scenario, the global delay in-
519 creases as one transitions from a solution mostly based on cherry-pickings
520 to a solution purely based on regulations. Furthermore, the distributions of
521 delays for solutions based on regulation are concentrated to higher values.

522 According to Tables B.2 and B.5, for the scenarios without capacity re-
523 duction shown in Fig. 6a the relative ATFM delay reduction of the OR with
524 respect to the GR ranges between 2 and 26% when using ICO-optimised
525 opening schemes, and between 5 and 34% when using post-ops opening
526 schemes. This is a positive assertion that a significant delay reduction could
527 be achieved by simply optimising regulations in a centralised manner.

528 Results for the scenarios shown in Fig. 6a also indicate that combining
529 regulations to address major overloads with some cherry-picking measures
530 for the residuals could result in even more global delay reduction. When
531 comparing the H solutions to the GR solutions, the relative delay reduction
532 ranges from 13 to 36% when using ICO-optimised opening schemes, and
533 between 11 and 38% when using post-ops opening schemes. The H+ achieves
534 considerably better results than the H by relying more on cherry-picking
535 measures to resolve overloads. For this model, the delay reduction with
536 respect to the GR ranges from 23 to 64% when using ICO-optimised opening
537 schemes, and between 24 and 59% when using post-ops opening schemes.

538 Following the trend, the CP presents a delay reduction with respect to the
539 analogous GR solutions ranging from 77 to 83% when using ICO-optimised
540 opening schemes, and between 59 and 74% when using post-ops opening

(a) Without capacity reductions due to weather

(b) With ICO opening scheme

Figure 6: Delay distribution per flight

541 schemes. The CP model, however, was not able to solve 2 out of the 8
 542 scenarios using post-ops opening schemes without capacity reduction, due
 543 to the unrealistic initial overloads. Furthermore, Fig. 6a indicates that the
 544 delay distribution of the CP solutions presents severe positive skewness, with
 545 a long tail on the right. When looking at Tables B.2 and B.5, this statement
 546 is evidenced: the average delay per flight delayed by more than 30 min and
 547 the maximum delay per flight are, in most of the cases, significantly higher
 548 than those reported by the other models. This means that the CP has to
 549 penalise few flights for the benefit of the global (network-wide) delay.

550 The impact of the weather forecast can be observed in Fig. 6b. In several
 551 cases, the forecast made at D-1 was more pessimistic than that made at D0,
 552 resulting in higher delays. In many other cases, the opposite happened.

553 Figure 7 shows the absolute delay change distribution per flight. As
 554 discussed in Section 5.1.3, this metric acts as a proxy for the model’s stability.
 555 As in Fig. 6a, each cell represents a traffic situation, and the colour indicates
 556 the source of the opening schemes from which capacities were derived.

Figure 7: Absolute delay change (ADC) distribution per flight

557 Figure 7 suggests that the stability increases when moving from a solution
 558 fully based on regulations to one fully based on cherry-picking measures.
 559 This rule does not always apply to the CP model, whose ADC’s maximum,

560 average and standard deviation are (sometimes) higher than those of the
561 other models (i.e., delay assignment at D-1 differs from that at D0), especially
562 in the scenarios where post-ops opening schemes were considered. Thus, in
563 terms of stability, the hybrid variants appear to be the most appealing.

564 5.2.2. *Delay distribution per airspace user*

565 One could argue that even if the CP model significantly reduces the total
566 ATFM delay required to resolve overloads as well as the number of delayed
567 flights, justice is compromised because the first-planned, first-served rule of
568 CASA is not imposed as hard constraint. The objective of this section is to
569 compare the solution proposed by the different models from the point of view
570 of the airspace user, in terms of total delay and maximum delay (keeping in
571 mind, however, that the airline's primary concern is cost). It should be noted
572 that only the set of airlines which cumulative number of operations, ordered
573 by frequency, represented 75% of the total traffic during the 4 dates and 2
574 periods considered in the experiment were selected for the analysis.

575 Figures 8 and 9 show the pairwise relationship of the different models for
576 the total and maximum delay per airspace user, respectively. In this kind of
577 plot, each dot corresponds to one airspace user. Points above the identity
578 line indicate that the model in the vertical axis assigned more delay than the
579 model in the horizontal axis. The diagonal plots represent the distribution
580 of the delay assigned by the model. Figures 8a and 9a show the pairwise
581 relationship for the scenarios without capacity reduction, as a function of the
582 opening schemes used to derive capacities; while Figure 8b and 9b show the
583 pairwise relationship for the scenarios with ICO-optimised opening schemes,
584 as a function of the NWP forecast used to derive capacity reductions.

585 Figure 8 suggest that, independently of the scenario, the vast majority of
586 European airlines would be given less total delay if greedy regulations were
587 optimised and progressively replaced with massive cherry-picking measures.
588 In the last row of Figs. 8a and 8b, one can easily notice that the cloud of
589 points approaches the identity line from above when moving from the left
590 (GR) to the right (CP) cell, but (in general) points do not cross that barrier.

591 The first columns of Figs. 9a and 9b reveal that the maximum delay
592 assigned by the CP was higher than the other models for many airspace users
593 in plenty of scenarios. In addition, a surprising conclusion can be obtained
594 from Fig. 9: the hybrid variants outperform the CP in many cases and only
595 slightly underperform the GR in a few, in terms of maximum delay.

Figure 8: Total delay change per airline (min)

Figure 9: Maximum delay change per airline (min)

596 *5.2.3. Delay distribution per air navigation service provider*

597 In Europe, air navigation service providers (ANSPs) are attributed with
 598 the delay generated by the ATFM measures that are associated with their
 599 traffic volumes, applying specific rules and exceptions that are out of the

600 scope of this paper. In any case, the delay attribution scheme encourages
 601 ANSPs to be as efficient and effective as possible in their local ATFM mea-
 602 sures. The models proposed herein, however, optimise the set of ATFM
 603 measures in a centralised manner for the benefit of the entire air transporta-
 604 tion network, regardless of where delays are applied. Accordingly, it might
 605 be the case that most of the delay is systematically attributed to the same
 606 ANSP. This section aims to compare the solution proposed by the different
 607 models from the point of view of the ANSP, in terms of total delay.

608 Figure 10 shows the pairwise relationship of the different models for the
 609 total delay per ANSP. In this figure, each dot corresponds to one ANSP.
 610 Points above the identity line indicate that the model in the vertical axis
 611 attributed more delay to the ANSP than the model in the horizontal axis.
 612 The diagonal plots represent the distribution of the delay attributed by the
 613 model (per ANSP). Figure 10a shows the pairwise relationship for the scenar-
 614 ios without capacity reduction, as a function of the opening schemes used
 615 to derive capacities; while Figure 10b shows the pairwise relationship for the
 616 scenarios with ICO-optimised opening schemes, as a function of the weather
 617 forecast used to derive capacity reductions.

Figure 10: Total delay change per air navigation service provider (min)

618 The same conclusions as for the airspace users apply to the ANSPs in-
 619 volved in the ISOBAR project: both French and Spanish ANSPs would face
 620 less delay if greedy regulations were optimised and gradually replaced with

621 cherry-picking measures; and hybrid variants appear to be very appealing
622 because they provide results similar to the CP without causing significant
623 disruption in the current ATFM mindset.

624 **6. Conclusions**

625 This paper compared the performance of various temporal air traffic flow
626 management (ATFM) models, progressively transitioning from a solution
627 based on greedy regulations to a futuristic solution based on massive cherry-
628 picking measures. The main findings of this study indicate that simply opti-
629 mising regulations in a centralised manner could result in a valuable reduc-
630 tion of the global delay. Results also suggest that increasing the number of
631 cherry-picking measures while limiting the use of regulations to major over-
632 loads would reduce delay and the number of delayed flights even more. The
633 hybrid variants, which are another contribution of this paper, are used to
634 combine regulations and cherry-picking measures. The best results in terms
635 of total delay, however, are reported by the massive cherry-picking model.

636 Figures also show that using more and more cherry-picking measures
637 instead of regulations would reduce total delay per airspace user and that
638 attributed to different air navigation service providers. The hybrid variants,
639 on the other hand, show superior results in terms of maximum delay per
640 airspace user, and appear to be the most appealing solutions for obtaining
641 significant benefits without major disruptions in current system. Another
642 benefit of hybrid variants is that their solutions are more consistent when
643 changing the capacity reduction values with the convective weather forecasts.

644 In nominal situations with moderate overloads, limited traffic adjustments
645 with cherry-picking measures could be sufficient. In case of critical situations,
646 substantial traffic adjustments with regulations are still required. The dis-
647 advantage of regulations is that they affect all flights entering the congested
648 traffic volume, regardless of their contribution to the problem or business
649 values for airspace users. Cherry-picking measures, on the other hand, are
650 assigned to specific flights in such a way that the total delay is minimised.

651 As a matter of fact, however, no ordinary human brain could ever master
652 hundreds of regulations and cherry-picking measures. The ATFM models
653 presented in this paper are based on artificial intelligence techniques and are
654 intended to assist flow managers in critical scenarios in applying the most
655 appropriate set of measures while taking into account various factors like
656 total delay, maximum delay per flight, number of measures, stability, etc.

657 It should be noted that each flight has its own sophisticated (and cer-
658 tainly non-linear) cost structure that only the airspace user is aware of. If
659 a flight is delayed to the point where an important milestone or constraint
660 is missed (e.g., a night curfew infringement), the operational costs of the
661 airspace user may be severely impacted (Pilon et al., 2019). The models in
662 this paper determine the optimal measures that minimise total delay, but the
663 cost is what actually matters to airspace users. Future work must account
664 for the cost of delays in both optimisation process and evaluation metrics.
665 Taking into account cost of delay in the optimisation process is challenging,
666 as airspace users do not disclose their financial information. One option to in-
667 clude the cost of delay into the optimisation might be a charging scheme that
668 allows airspace users to (implicitly) prioritise specific flights. See for exam-
669 ple (Künne and Strauss, 2022). Finally, the cherry-picking measures used
670 herein are obtained by solving the simplest slot allocation problem. Future
671 work must consider more sophisticated variants proposed in the literature.

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748 **Appendix A. Execution times**

749 For the scenarios investigated in this paper, the typical execution time per
750 algorithm using the Red Hat Enterprise Linux release 8.5 with 12x Intel(R)
751 Xeon(R) W-2235 CPU @ 3.80GHz processors and 256GB of RAM is:

- 752 • Greedy regulations (Algorithm 3): Each CASA run takes around .5
753 s. The greedy regulations algorithm converges, most of the time, in 5
754 iterations. Therefore, the execution time is around 3 s.
- 755 • ALNS (Algorithm 2): in the current configuration, the ALNS consists
756 of executing the greedy regulations algorithm 200 times. Accordingly,
757 the execution time is around 10 min.
- 758 • Slot allocation problem (Eq. 2): at most 1 min by using the CBC
759 (COIN-OR Branch and Cut) mixed integer linear programming solver
760 (release 2.10.5).

761 Note that the hybrid models need to run both ALNS and slot allocation
762 problem in sequence. Therefore, the estimated execution time is 11 min
763 (assuming the recommended 200 iterations for the ALNS step). Furthermore,
764 these figures only reflect the scenarios investigated herein, which consider the
765 AM or PM periods and the flights crossing the Spanish and French airspace.

766 **Appendix B. Detailed performance metrics**

Table B.2: Performance metrics with ICO opening scheme and NA capacity reduction

Traffic situation		Model	Performance metric, min or # (with respect to GR, %)					
Date	Period		Sum	Count	Count>30	Avg.	Avg.>30	Max.
26 Jul 2019	AM	GR	44071 (0)	1973 (0)	492 (0)	22 (0)	52 (0)	84 (0)
		OR	37692 (-14)	1950 (-1)	423 (-14)	19 (-13)	44 (-14)	69 (-18)
		H	30924 (-30)	1708 (-13)	363 (-26)	18 (-19)	45 (-13)	64 (-24)
		H+	23666 (-46)	1441 (-27)	248 (-50)	16 (-26)	44 (-14)	71 (-15)
		CP	8591 (-81)	828 (-58)	66 (-87)	10 (-54)	56 (8)	87 (4)
	PM	GR	26428 (0)	1604 (0)	167 (0)	16 (0)	57 (0)	83 (0)
		OR	25080 (-5)	1534 (-4)	166 (-1)	16 (-1)	57 (0)	83 (0)
		H	22764 (-14)	1515 (-6)	142 (-15)	15 (-9)	57 (1)	79 (-5)
		H+	20193 (-24)	1305 (-19)	142 (-15)	15 (-6)	57 (1)	79 (-5)
		CP	6759 (-74)	718 (-55)	50 (-70)	9 (-43)	53 (-6)	89 (7)
27 Jul 2019	AM	GR	41153 (0)	2031 (0)	373 (0)	20 (0)	51 (0)	80 (0)
		OR	39238 (-5)	1916 (-6)	378 (1)	20 (1)	52 (2)	80 (0)
		H	31235 (-24)	1705 (-16)	309 (-17)	18 (-10)	49 (-4)	71 (-11)
		H+	26140 (-36)	1425 (-30)	269 (-28)	18 (-9)	50 (-2)	71 (-11)
		CP	9217 (-78)	800 (-61)	76 (-80)	12 (-43)	60 (18)	90 (12)
	PM	GR	25983 (0)	1737 (0)	83 (0)	15 (0)	38 (0)	52 (0)
		OR	22374 (-14)	1627 (-6)	52 (-37)	14 (-8)	35 (-8)	45 (-13)
		H	18989 (-27)	1637 (-6)	10 (-88)	12 (-22)	32 (-16)	34 (-35)
		H+	13102 (-50)	1213 (-30)	5 (-94)	11 (-28)	33 (-13)	38 (-27)
		CP	5513 (-79)	702 (-60)	31 (-63)	8 (-47)	53 (39)	88 (69)
09 Aug 2019	AM	GR	44403 (0)	2108 (0)	552 (0)	21 (0)	42 (0)	65 (0)
		OR	43323 (-2)	2017 (-4)	559 (1)	21 (2)	42 (-1)	64 (-2)
		H	34508 (-22)	1836 (-13)	431 (-22)	19 (-11)	40 (-4)	61 (-6)
		H+	25755 (-42)	1496 (-29)	273 (-51)	17 (-18)	39 (-7)	58 (-11)
		CP	10166 (-77)	882 (-58)	86 (-84)	12 (-45)	59 (41)	90 (38)
	PM	GR	26043 (0)	1716 (0)	208 (0)	15 (0)	36 (0)	42 (0)
		OR	19154 (-26)	1561 (-9)	9 (-96)	12 (-19)	32 (-12)	33 (-21)
		H	16649 (-36)	1502 (-12)	6 (-97)	11 (-27)	33 (-8)	39 (-7)
		H+	10658 (-59)	1135 (-34)	5 (-98)	9 (-38)	38 (6)	45 (7)
		CP	4514 (-83)	645 (-62)	22 (-89)	7 (-54)	46 (27)	77 (83)
27 Aug 2019	AM	GR	31707 (0)	1743 (0)	221 (0)	18 (0)	58 (0)	102 (0)
		OR	28899 (-9)	1665 (-4)	196 (-11)	17 (-5)	59 (2)	102 (0)
		H	27577 (-13)	1594 (-9)	205 (-7)	17 (-5)	57 (-1)	101 (-1)
		H+	18405 (-42)	1282 (-26)	141 (-36)	14 (-21)	53 (-8)	82 (-20)
		CP	5881 (-81)	739 (-58)	29 (-87)	8 (-56)	51 (-11)	88 (-14)
	PM	GR	23302 (0)	1500 (0)	194 (0)	16 (0)	43 (0)	58 (0)
		OR	20205 (-13)	1416 (-6)	145 (-25)	14 (-8)	41 (-3)	55 (-5)
		H	19707 (-15)	1427 (-5)	168 (-13)	14 (-11)	41 (-4)	54 (-7)
		H+	15400 (-34)	1168 (-22)	140 (-28)	13 (-15)	38 (-10)	51 (-12)
		CP	5360 (-77)	663 (-56)	35 (-82)	8 (-48)	51 (20)	84 (45)

Table B.3: Performance metrics with ICO opening scheme and D-1 capacity reduction

Traffic situation		Model	Performance metric, min or # (with respect to GR, %)					
Date	Period		Sum	Count	Count>30	Avg.	Avg.>30	Max.
26 Jul 2019	AM	GR	44431 (0)	2156 (0)	455 (0)	21 (0)	47 (0)	71 (0)
		OR	38857 (-13)	1947 (-10)	405 (-11)	20 (-3)	47 (-1)	69 (-3)
		H	33497 (-25)	1851 (-14)	337 (-26)	18 (-12)	47 (0)	68 (-4)
		H+	27462 (-38)	1626 (-25)	293 (-36)	17 (-18)	44 (-8)	62 (-13)
		CP	12029 (-73)	914 (-58)	113 (-75)	13 (-36)	59 (25)	90 (27)
	PM	GR	26507 (0)	1615 (0)	167 (0)	16 (0)	57 (0)	83 (0)
		OR	25331 (-4)	1541 (-5)	166 (-1)	16 (0)	57 (0)	83 (0)
		H	22687 (-14)	1503 (-7)	144 (-14)	15 (-8)	57 (1)	79 (-5)
		H+	20010 (-25)	1287 (-20)	141 (-16)	16 (-5)	58 (2)	79 (-5)
		CP	6803 (-74)	727 (-55)	49 (-71)	9 (-43)	53 (-6)	89 (7)
27 Jul 2019	AM	GR	64510 (0)	2339 (0)	801 (0)	28 (0)	52 (0)	89 (0)
		OR	55629 (-14)	2184 (-7)	717 (-10)	25 (-8)	49 (-7)	82 (-8)
		H	34548 (-46)	1919 (-18)	379 (-53)	18 (-35)	44 (-16)	71 (-20)
		H+	38590 (-40)	1844 (-21)	450 (-44)	21 (-24)	48 (-7)	82 (-8)
		CP	16620 (-74)	1062 (-55)	166 (-79)	16 (-43)	60 (16)	90 (1)
	PM	GR	27033 (0)	1816 (0)	86 (0)	15 (0)	38 (0)	52 (0)
		OR	24018 (-11)	1698 (-6)	84 (-2)	14 (-5)	38 (0)	52 (0)
		H	20181 (-25)	1746 (-4)	20 (-77)	12 (-22)	33 (-13)	37 (-29)
		H+	13670 (-49)	1265 (-30)	8 (-91)	11 (-27)	36 (-6)	53 (2)
		CP	5824 (-78)	737 (-59)	37 (-57)	8 (-47)	50 (31)	88 (69)
09 Aug 2019	AM	GR	48517 (0)	2129 (0)	599 (0)	23 (0)	45 (0)	86 (0)
		OR	46305 (-5)	2053 (-4)	576 (-4)	23 (-1)	45 (0)	86 (0)
		H	41153 (-15)	1932 (-9)	486 (-19)	21 (-7)	45 (-1)	84 (-2)
		H+	28877 (-40)	1617 (-24)	299 (-50)	18 (-22)	44 (-3)	78 (-9)
		CP	12920 (-73)	912 (-57)	128 (-79)	14 (-38)	62 (37)	90 (5)
	PM	GR	26223 (0)	1722 (0)	208 (0)	15 (0)	36 (0)	42 (0)
		OR	19514 (-26)	1595 (-7)	8 (-96)	12 (-20)	32 (-12)	33 (-21)
		H	16912 (-36)	1553 (-10)	3 (-99)	11 (-28)	34 (-6)	39 (-7)
		H+	10854 (-59)	1145 (-34)	7 (-97)	9 (-38)	37 (2)	45 (7)
		CP	4705 (-82)	655 (-62)	24 (-88)	7 (-53)	48 (33)	85 (102)
27 Aug 2019	AM	GR	37746 (0)	1970 (0)	280 (0)	19 (0)	53 (0)	103 (0)
		OR	34727 (-8)	1859 (-6)	260 (-7)	19 (-3)	53 (-1)	105 (2)
		H	31308 (-17)	1793 (-9)	252 (-10)	17 (-9)	51 (-4)	102 (-1)
		H+	24631 (-35)	1508 (-23)	181 (-35)	16 (-15)	55 (3)	101 (-2)
		CP	8932 (-76)	868 (-56)	67 (-76)	10 (-46)	51 (-3)	88 (-15)
	PM	GR	23810 (0)	1572 (0)	193 (0)	15 (0)	42 (0)	58 (0)
		OR	21591 (-9)	1532 (-3)	151 (-22)	14 (-7)	41 (-3)	56 (-3)
		H	20468 (-14)	1460 (-7)	171 (-11)	14 (-7)	41 (-4)	53 (-9)
		H+	15615 (-34)	1232 (-22)	119 (-38)	13 (-16)	38 (-11)	45 (-22)
		CP	5600 (-76)	695 (-56)	36 (-81)	8 (-47)	51 (19)	84 (45)

Table B.4: Performance metrics with ICO opening scheme and D0 capacity reduction

Traffic situation		Model	Performance metric, min or # (with respect to GR, %)					
Date	Period		Sum	Count	Count>30	Avg.	Avg.>30	Max.
26 Jul 2019	AM	GR	52457 (0)	2226 (0)	570 (0)	24 (0)	52 (0)	82 (0)
		OR	45324 (-14)	2015 (-9)	498 (-13)	22 (-5)	50 (-4)	79 (-4)
		H	33428 (-36)	1865 (-16)	328 (-42)	18 (-24)	47 (-9)	69 (-16)
		H+	30008 (-43)	1749 (-21)	265 (-54)	17 (-27)	45 (-14)	59 (-28)
		CP	10526 (-80)	907 (-59)	90 (-84)	12 (-51)	56 (7)	89 (9)
	PM	GR	59769 (0)	2160 (0)	759 (0)	28 (0)	51 (0)	96 (0)
		OR	39587 (-34)	1632 (-24)	511 (-33)	24 (-12)	49 (-5)	96 (0)
		H	27956 (-53)	1759 (-19)	236 (-69)	16 (-43)	42 (-18)	74 (-23)
		H+	26681 (-55)	1703 (-21)	185 (-76)	16 (-43)	44 (-14)	85 (-11)
		CP	19392 (-68)	1046 (-52)	212 (-72)	19 (-33)	59 (16)	90 (-6)
27 Jul 2019	AM	GR	56930 (0)	2266 (0)	652 (0)	25 (0)	50 (0)	87 (0)
		OR	53495 (-6)	2316 (2)	589 (-10)	23 (-8)	48 (-5)	82 (-6)
		H	43943 (-23)	2204 (-3)	448 (-31)	20 (-21)	43 (-14)	71 (-18)
		H+	39355 (-31)	1819 (-20)	455 (-30)	22 (-14)	49 (-3)	80 (-8)
		CP	13150 (-77)	990 (-56)	117 (-82)	13 (-47)	62 (23)	90 (3)
	PM	GR	47385 (0)	2248 (0)	484 (0)	21 (0)	45 (0)	85 (0)
		OR	39126 (-17)	1993 (-11)	417 (-14)	20 (-7)	41 (-9)	67 (-21)
		H	22463 (-53)	1720 (-23)	93 (-81)	13 (-38)	37 (-18)	48 (-44)
		H+	16850 (-64)	1497 (-33)	34 (-93)	11 (-47)	37 (-18)	60 (-29)
		CP	9546 (-80)	932 (-59)	70 (-86)	10 (-51)	55 (22)	89 (5)
09 Aug 2019	AM	GR	49637 (0)	2197 (0)	616 (0)	23 (0)	44 (0)	81 (0)
		OR	47076 (-5)	2124 (-3)	555 (-10)	22 (-2)	45 (0)	87 (7)
		H	40664 (-18)	2052 (-7)	481 (-22)	20 (-12)	44 (0)	79 (-2)
		H+	29698 (-40)	1679 (-24)	298 (-52)	18 (-22)	44 (-2)	77 (-5)
		CP	12663 (-74)	942 (-57)	120 (-81)	13 (-41)	61 (37)	90 (11)
	PM	GR	30546 (0)	2065 (0)	144 (0)	15 (0)	36 (0)	42 (0)
		OR	23917 (-22)	1810 (-12)	88 (-39)	13 (-11)	34 (-5)	41 (-2)
		H	21821 (-29)	1782 (-14)	75 (-48)	12 (-17)	35 (-2)	58 (38)
		H+	13782 (-55)	1338 (-35)	37 (-74)	10 (-30)	38 (7)	79 (88)
		CP	7879 (-74)	806 (-61)	62 (-57)	10 (-34)	54 (52)	87 (107)
27 Aug 2019	AM	GR	41931 (0)	2056 (0)	319 (0)	20 (0)	51 (0)	102 (0)
		OR	35258 (-16)	2032 (-1)	233 (-27)	17 (-15)	36 (-29)	51 (-50)
		H	32673 (-22)	1841 (-10)	277 (-13)	18 (-13)	48 (-5)	101 (-1)
		H+	26323 (-37)	1568 (-24)	214 (-33)	17 (-18)	51 (1)	100 (-2)
		CP	10101 (-76)	926 (-55)	79 (-75)	11 (-47)	51 (1)	88 (-14)
	PM	GR	42367 (0)	2236 (0)	350 (0)	19 (0)	46 (0)	77 (0)
		OR	33340 (-21)	1915 (-14)	241 (-31)	17 (-8)	43 (-6)	64 (-17)
		H	31184 (-26)	2056 (-8)	199 (-43)	15 (-20)	46 (-1)	72 (-6)
		H+	20026 (-53)	1536 (-31)	123 (-65)	13 (-31)	41 (-11)	84 (9)
		CP	10683 (-75)	986 (-56)	85 (-76)	11 (-43)	56 (23)	89 (16)

Table B.5: Performance metrics with DDR opening scheme and NA capacity reduction

Traffic situation		Model	Performance metric, min or # (with respect to GR, %)					
Date	Period		Sum	Count	Count>30	Avg.	Avg.>30	Max.
26 Jul 2019	AM	GR	50774 (0)	2179 (0)	613 (0)	23 (0)	45 (0)	68 (0)
		OR	48106 (-5)	2104 (-3)	594 (-3)	23 (-2)	44 (-1)	68 (0)
		H	43687 (-14)	2137 (-2)	501 (-18)	20 (-12)	42 (-5)	66 (-3)
		H+	35132 (-31)	1902 (-13)	390 (-36)	18 (-21)	42 (-7)	65 (-4)
		CP	13010 (-74)	1058 (-51)	117 (-81)	12 (-47)	58 (30)	90 (32)
27 Jul 2019	AM	GR	72603 (0)	2528 (0)	995 (0)	29 (0)	50 (0)	92 (0)
		OR	51724 (-29)	2152 (-15)	654 (-34)	24 (-16)	45 (-10)	71 (-23)
		H	50794 (-30)	2316 (-8)	628 (-37)	22 (-24)	45 (-10)	80 (-13)
		H+	43323 (-40)	2073 (-18)	558 (-44)	21 (-27)	44 (-12)	67 (-27)
		CP	25465 (-65)	1325 (-48)	276 (-72)	19 (-33)	64 (28)	90 (-2)
	PM	GR	28211 (0)	1871 (0)	146 (0)	15 (0)	40 (0)	49 (0)
		OR	27888 (-1)	1855 (-1)	146 (0)	15 (0)	40 (0)	49 (0)
		H	25182 (-11)	1920 (3)	132 (-10)	13 (-13)	40 (0)	49 (0)
		H+	21549 (-24)	1679 (-10)	113 (-23)	13 (-15)	38 (-4)	51 (4)
		CP	10023 (-64)	954 (-49)	86 (-41)	11 (-30)	53 (34)	88 (80)
09 Aug 2019	AM	GR	64262 (0)	2255 (0)	894 (0)	28 (0)	50 (0)	87 (0)
		OR	54324 (-15)	2210 (-2)	710 (-21)	25 (-14)	45 (-10)	75 (-14)
		H	40094 (-38)	2020 (-10)	461 (-48)	20 (-30)	45 (-9)	88 (1)
		H+	33627 (-48)	1895 (-16)	368 (-59)	18 (-38)	45 (-10)	89 (2)
		CP	26184 (-59)	1186 (-47)	303 (-66)	22 (-23)	65 (32)	90 (3)
27 Aug 2019	AM	GR	41652 (0)	1748 (0)	524 (0)	24 (0)	43 (0)	66 (0)
		OR	30019 (-28)	1412 (-19)	367 (-30)	21 (-11)	41 (-6)	59 (-11)
		H	26915 (-35)	1602 (-8)	275 (-48)	17 (-29)	40 (-8)	54 (-18)
		H+	25362 (-39)	1524 (-13)	264 (-50)	17 (-30)	40 (-8)	54 (-18)
		CP	16964 (-59)	916 (-48)	187 (-64)	19 (-22)	62 (43)	90 (36)
	PM	GR	42279 (0)	1999 (0)	510 (0)	21 (0)	43 (0)	68 (0)
		OR	39791 (-6)	1971 (-1)	433 (-15)	20 (-5)	43 (0)	64 (-6)
		H	36766 (-13)	2049 (3)	386 (-24)	18 (-15)	39 (-9)	58 (-15)
		H+	29106 (-31)	1654 (-17)	337 (-34)	18 (-17)	39 (-9)	61 (-10)
		CP	14044 (-67)	993 (-50)	142 (-72)	14 (-33)	58 (33)	89 (31)

Table B.6: Performance metrics with DDR opening scheme and D-1 capacity reduction

Traffic situation		Model	Performance metric, min or # (with respect to GR, %)					
Date	Period		Sum	Count	Count>30	Avg.	Avg.>30	Max.
26 Jul 2019	AM	GR	57808 (0)	2361 (0)	690 (0)	24 (0)	47 (0)	76 (0)
		OR	53190 (-8)	2233 (-5)	613 (-11)	24 (-3)	46 (-2)	72 (-5)
		H	47615 (-18)	2265 (-4)	557 (-19)	21 (-14)	44 (-6)	70 (-8)
		H+	39975 (-31)	2070 (-12)	465 (-33)	19 (-21)	42 (-10)	65 (-14)
		CP	16142 (-72)	1159 (-51)	151 (-78)	14 (-43)	61 (29)	90 (18)
27 Jul 2019	PM	GR	31715 (0)	2058 (0)	152 (0)	15 (0)	39 (0)	49 (0)
		OR	29632 (-7)	1958 (-5)	144 (-5)	15 (-2)	39 (0)	49 (0)
		H	25351 (-20)	2112 (3)	24 (-84)	12 (-22)	33 (-16)	37 (-24)
		H+	22949 (-28)	1795 (-13)	106 (-30)	13 (-17)	40 (1)	51 (4)
		CP	10639 (-66)	1010 (-51)	89 (-41)	11 (-32)	53 (35)	88 (80)
09 Aug 2019	AM	GR	69870 (0)	2293 (0)	951 (0)	30 (0)	53 (0)	96 (0)
		OR	63007 (-10)	2257 (-2)	851 (-11)	28 (-8)	50 (-6)	86 (-10)
		H	44220 (-37)	2114 (-8)	536 (-44)	21 (-31)	47 (-13)	88 (-8)
		H+	38880 (-44)	1988 (-13)	479 (-50)	20 (-36)	45 (-16)	89 (-7)
		CP	30516 (-56)	1259 (-45)	346 (-64)	24 (-20)	67 (26)	90 (-6)
27 Aug 2019	AM	GR	50596 (0)	1908 (0)	646 (0)	27 (0)	49 (0)	85 (0)
		OR	36799 (-27)	1636 (-14)	486 (-25)	22 (-15)	43 (-12)	65 (-24)
		H	32653 (-35)	1747 (-8)	385 (-40)	19 (-30)	43 (-12)	69 (-19)
		H+	30766 (-39)	1686 (-12)	366 (-43)	18 (-31)	42 (-14)	80 (-6)
		CP	21770 (-57)	1061 (-44)	250 (-61)	21 (-23)	61 (25)	90 (6)
27 Aug 2019	PM	GR	42784 (0)	2058 (0)	515 (0)	21 (0)	43 (0)	68 (0)
		OR	38557 (-10)	1973 (-4)	420 (-18)	20 (-6)	41 (-4)	60 (-12)
		H	37271 (-13)	2032 (-1)	432 (-16)	18 (-12)	41 (-6)	60 (-12)
		H+	30851 (-28)	1799 (-13)	302 (-41)	17 (-18)	41 (-6)	60 (-12)
		CP	14203 (-67)	1015 (-51)	137 (-73)	14 (-33)	59 (36)	90 (32)

Table B.7: Performance metrics with DDR opening scheme and D0 capacity reduction

Traffic situation		Model	Performance metric, min or # (with respect to GR, %)					
Date	Period		Sum	Count	Count>30	Avg.	Avg.>30	Max.
26 Jul 2019	AM	GR	61577 (0)	2469 (0)	749 (0)	25 (0)	47 (0)	73 (0)
		OR	53997 (-12)	2289 (-7)	616 (-18)	24 (-5)	45 (-3)	68 (-7)
		H	49075 (-20)	2259 (-9)	533 (-29)	22 (-13)	46 (-2)	71 (-3)
		H+	43326 (-30)	2065 (-16)	496 (-34)	21 (-16)	44 (-7)	63 (-14)
		CP	15724 (-74)	1162 (-53)	147 (-80)	14 (-46)	59 (26)	90 (23)
27 Jul 2019	PM	GR	57543 (0)	2437 (0)	656 (0)	24 (0)	44 (0)	76 (0)
		OR	38619 (-33)	2087 (-14)	311 (-53)	19 (-22)	36 (-18)	49 (-36)
		H	35678 (-38)	2208 (-9)	255 (-61)	16 (-32)	36 (-17)	86 (13)
		H+	29438 (-49)	2004 (-18)	164 (-75)	15 (-38)	38 (-13)	89 (17)
		CP	26029 (-55)	1351 (-45)	297 (-55)	19 (-18)	62 (41)	90 (18)
09 Aug 2019	AM	GR	70448 (0)	2286 (0)	980 (0)	31 (0)	54 (0)	95 (0)
		OR	63761 (-9)	2213 (-3)	884 (-10)	29 (-7)	51 (-5)	93 (-2)
		H	44494 (-37)	2112 (-8)	562 (-43)	21 (-32)	46 (-14)	88 (-7)
		H+	40266 (-43)	2018 (-12)	511 (-48)	20 (-35)	45 (-16)	89 (-6)
		CP	30741 (-56)	1275 (-44)	352 (-64)	24 (-22)	67 (24)	90 (-5)
27 Aug 2019	AM	GR	54204 (0)	1944 (0)	750 (0)	28 (0)	50 (0)	87 (0)
		OR	40925 (-24)	1701 (-12)	556 (-26)	24 (-14)	45 (-9)	70 (-20)
		H	38268 (-29)	1891 (-3)	454 (-39)	20 (-27)	44 (-11)	79 (-9)
		H+	35882 (-34)	1784 (-8)	457 (-39)	20 (-28)	44 (-12)	87 (0)
		CP	25211 (-53)	1087 (-44)	297 (-60)	23 (-17)	63 (27)	90 (3)